

Complex Formation of Vanadium(V) with Salicylhydroxamic Acid in MIBK : Photometric Methods of Determination of Vanadium in Alloy Steel and Ores

S. P. BAG, A. B. CHATTERJEE, A. K. CHAKRABARTI and P. R. CHAKRABORTY*

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 8 July 1981, revised 1 December 1981, accepted 12 August 1982

Reactions of vanadium(V) with N-salicylhydroxamic acid under varying conditions of pH and acidity and extraction behaviour of binary and ternary complexes in methyl isobutylketone are reported. New sensitive and selective photometric methods for trace determination of vanadium(V) in absence or presence of thiocyanate and its applications in the analyses of high speed steel, ilmenite and bauxite are also described.

In this paper we report the use of a hydroxamic acid (N-SHA) where a phenolic -OH group is attached to the *ortho* position of the phenyl ring¹⁻³. In N-AHA molecule a basic -NH₂ group is attached to *ortho* position and the mixed-ligand extraction has been described⁴. Formations of different complexes of vanadium(V) with N-SHA under varying conditions of pH have been investigated along with ternary extraction involving thiocyanate. The sensitivity and selectivity of the determinations have been found to increase considerably both in binary and ternary extractions in methyl isobutylketone (mibk) even in presence of moderate excess of Fe(III) and Ti(IV). Fe(III) and Ti(IV) interfered in almost all the procedures mentioned with N-aryhydroxamic acids and amines either in extraction or in direct measurement in aqueous medium. Analyses of standard alloy steel, ilmenite and bauxite were also undertaken and the methods worked successfully⁵⁻⁷.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions: A stock solution of vanadium was prepared from ammonium vanadate (E. Merck) and standardized⁸. The reagent, N-SHA, was prepared by the reported method⁹. Standard reagent solutions (1% w/v) and of desired strengths in pure mibk were used directly for extractions. A standard 2% aqueous solution of ammonium thiocyanate was used in ternary extraction. All other chemicals, reagents and solvents used in the experiments were of A. R. grade quality.

Apparatus: Measurements were made with Hilger-Uvispek and Spektromom 204 spectrophotometers with matched 1 cm quartz or glass cells. A Systronics pH-meter (324, India) was used for pH measurements.

Recommended procedure:

(A) **Binary extraction, pH 3.1:** An aliquot of vanadium solution (1.963×10^{-3} M) was taken in a

100 ml separatory funnel and the pH was adjusted by adding very dil HCl after 5 ml of 1% reagent was added to 10 ml of aqueous phase and 0.5 ml of 0.1 M HCl. It was shaken with an equal volume of organic phase (10 ml) for 5 min. The blue-violet complex extracted from pH 3.1 was drained out in a 50 ml beaker and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The extractions were repeated with 5 ml portions of the solvent. The combined extract was transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The volume was made up to the mark with pure solvent. The absorbance of the complex solution was measured at 575 nm against solvent blank. A calibration curve was constructed.

(B) **Binary extraction, 1.8 M HCl:** An aliquot of the metal solution (1.963×10^{-3} M) was taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel with 5 ml of 1% reagent. The pH was adjusted to 3.1 by adding 0.5 ml of 0.1 M HCl and the mixture was shaken with 10 ml of methyl isobutyl ketone. The acidity was then adjusted to 1.8 M HCl by adding 6 M HCl. The wine-red complex was extracted for 5 min. It was dried and transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark. The absorbance was measured against solvent blank at 510 nm. A calibration curve was also constructed.

(C) **Ternary extraction, pH 0.95/0.16 M HCl:** In the ternary extraction, the blue-violet complex was first extracted at pH 3.1 by adding 5 ml of 1% reagent and 0.5 ml of 0.1 M HCl for 2 min with 15 ml of methyl isobutyl ketone. 1 ml of 2% ammonium thiocyanate was added and the pH of the 15 ml aqueous phase was adjusted to 0.95. The blue-violet complex was again extracted for 8 min. The extractions were repeated with 5 ml portions of the solvent. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with pure solvent. A reagent blank was prepared similarly. The absorbance of the complex was measured against solvent

* At present Chemist, Indian Oxygen Limited, Calcutta.

at 540 nm. A calibration curve was also constructed.

Procedure for steel analysis: 0.5 g of steel sample was dissolved in 25 ml dilute sulphuric acid (1 : 1) and the solution was digested on a hot plate to a syrupy solution, repeating the addition of acid. It was then treated with 5 ml of conc nitric acid for complete digestion and evaporated to dryness. The solution was diluted with 50 ml water, boiled, filtered, and washed with hot acidulated water and finally with hot water. The cold filtrate and the washings were taken in a 250 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark. An aliquot of the steel solution was transferred and oxidised at room temperature with 0.1% KMnO_4 solution till the pink colour persisted. A hot solution of 15% NaOH solution was then added and the mixture boiled. The precipitate was filtered off and redissolved in dil HCl and the procedure was repeated several times. The filtrates were collected and boiled down to a low volume. The solution was cooled and vanadium content was determined following the recommended procedures A, B and C. The absorbance of the extracts was measured at 575, 510 and 540 nm for the respective complexes and the metal content determined separately.

Procedure for ore analysis: 0.5 g of finely powdered ore was fused with 9 g KHSO_4 and a few drops of H_2SO_4 in a silica crucible over a low flame to avoid spurning and a clear melt was obtained. The fused mass was cooled and leached with 1 : 9 H_2SO_4 acid. The solution was boiled and oxidised with a few drops of nitric acid. Iron and titanium was precipitated as hydroxides with an excess of 15% NaOH solution. Any adsorbed vanadium in the hydroxide was freed by double precipitation method. The filtrates were combined and the volume reduced to 0.5 ml by boiling. The cold solution was transferred into a 100 ml standard flask and the volume was made up with water. Different aliquots were taken and the metal was determined by procedures A, B and C using fluoride for traces of iron and titanium in the solution.

Procedure for bauxite: Bauxite sample was decomposed by alkaline flux. 0.5 g of the sample was fused for 2 hr with Na_2CO_3 (3-4 g) and NaOH (1 g) in a nickel crucible. The melt was cooled and leached with hot water and kept overnight. The aqueous extract of vanadium and other insoluble materials along with iron and titanium was filtered, transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume made up to the mark. The vanadium content was determined using appropriate amount of the solution.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance spectra: The absorbance spectra of binary and ternary chelates of vanadium(V) showed maximum at 575, 510 and 540 nm (Fig. 1). Since reagent blanks showed no absorbance in these regions the absorbance has been measured against solvent blank mibk.

Fig. 1. Spectral curves of the V(V) binary and ternary complexes. $\text{V(V)} = 7.853 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$; $\text{N-SHA} = 1.306 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; $\text{NH}_4\text{SCN} = 5.255 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.
Curve I - $\circ$: V(V)-N-SHA binary complex at pH=3.1,
II - $\circ$: V(V)-N-SHA binary complex at 1.8 M HCl,
III - $\bullet$: V(V)-N-SHA ternary complex at pH=0.95.

Optimum reaction conditions: The optimum pH range of extractions for blue-violet chelate was found to be 2.2-5.6 and pH was always adjusted to 3.1 for all measurements. At $\text{pH} < 2.2$ a shift of the maximum occurs with corresponding colour change towards red-violet. The intensity of wine-red complex is constant in the region 0.6-4.2 M HCl . It was observed that direct addition of 6 M HCl produced a very low absorbance. The complex is first extracted from pH 3.1 and then the acidity increased. An emulsion, requiring time to break, formed as acidity increased above 3.5 M HCl . All measurements were made at 1.8 M HCl for wine-red complex. The optimum acidity range for violet coloured mixed-ligand vanadium complex is pH 1.3 to 0.33 M HCl . This complex is formed from pH 1.8 to 3.0 M HCl , and separation and extraction is slow at $\text{pH} > 1.8$ and $> 0.8 \text{ M HCl}$ due to emulsion formation. Ternary extractions were made at pH 0.95/0.16 M HCl . The binary complex is first extracted from pH 3.0 and then a 0.16 M HCl acidity was maintained.

2.5 ml of 1%, 2.0 ml of 1% and 0.5 ml of 1% (w/v) reagent in mibk were found sufficient for full colour development of the respective complexes and their extractions. The optimum range is 2 to 10 ml of 1% for binary systems and 0.5-10 ml of 1% reagent for ternary system. 5 ml of 1% reagent used for all three extractive methods. Ternary complex is formed with 0.1 to 12 ml of 1% reagent with a fixed amount [1 ml of 2% (0.26 M)] of thiocyanate added and 0.5 ml of 1% reagent. With 5 ml of 1% reagent (N-SHA) the violet complex of vanadium(V) was formed with 0.01 to 10 ml of 2%

ammonium thiocyanate and 0.75 ml was found sufficient. A 5 ml of 2% solution was always used in the method.

The binary and ternary complexes are completely extracted within 4 to 5 and 7 to 9 min and show constant absorbance immediately after the volume is made up. The complexes are stable for more than 24 hr at room temperature (27°).

Calibration curve, optimum range and sensitivity : For solutions of varied amount of vanadium(V), fixed amounts of reagent (N-SHA) and thiocyanate solutions were utilized in the above procedures and absorbances were measured at 575, 510 and 540 nm, respectively. The systems obeyed Beer's law (Fig. 2) in the range 0.2-8 (blue-violet), 0.25-9 (wine-red) and 0.4-12 (violet) ppm

Fig. 2. Beer's law curves. N-SHA = $1.906 \times 10^{-2} M$; $NH_4SCN = 5.255 \times 10^{-2} M$.
 Plot I - O : V(V)-N-SHA binary complex at pH=3.1.
 II - O : V(V)-N-SHA binary complex at 1.8 M HCl.
 III - ● : V(V)-N-SHA-SCN ternary complex at 0.16 M HCl.

with optimum range obtained from Ringbom's plot⁹ as 2-6.5, 2-6 and 1-6 ppm, respectively. The % relative error per 1% absolute photometric error using Ayres' equation¹⁰ for the systems are 2.71, 2.72 and 2.73%, respectively.

The molar absorptivities are 5.71×10^4 (at 575 nm), 5.73×10^4 (at 510 nm) and 8.34×10^4 (at 540 nm) l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The corresponding Sandell sensitivities¹¹ are 0.00893, 0.0089 and 0.0061 μg cm⁻² V(V).

Interference studies : Solutions were prepared by the above procedures with 4 ppm vanadium(V) (25 ml) and different amounts of diverse ions at the pH acidity conditions. The ions were added before the reagent. Normally, Fe(III), Ti(IV), Mo(VI), W(VI), Zr(IV), Nb(V), Hf(IV) have low tolerance limits. Masking with fluoride ion is effective for moderate excess. Most of the metal ions do not

interfere in all the three systems. Anions have no other effect. The methods were found to be accurate and precise for analyses of geological materials and alloy. The results are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS
 [V(V)=0.1 mg, N-SHA=1% in mlbk, $NH_4SCN=2\%$ aq. solution]

Ions	Tolerance limits, mg		
	pH 3.1 575 nm	1.8 M HCl 510 nm	pH 0.95 540 nm
Acetate	10	10	20
Fluoride	20	10	20
Tartrate	50	45	30
Oxalate	2	8	20
Citrate	50	50	25
EDTA	1.5	40	10
Phosphate	10	75	50
Fe(III)	1	1.25	5*
Th(IV)	Int.	1	5*
Mo(VI)	1.5	1.25	1.25*
W(VI)	1	4.5	2.5*
Zr(IV)	5	6.25	6.25*
Hf(IV)	5	6.25	6.25*
Th(IV)	10	20	10
Nb(V)	1.25	1.25	1.25*
Ta(V)	1.25	1.25	3*
UO ₂ (II)	7.5	11.25	10
Co(II)	15	20	5
Ni(II)	10	15	5
Cu(II)	2.5	7.5	3.75
Mn(II)	4	20	12.5
Cr(III)	7.5	15	10
Al(III)	2.5	5	5
Zn(II)	7.5	15	10
Cd(II)	6.25	6.25	12.5
Pb(II)	10	20	15
Pd(II)	0.75	3.75	1

*Fluoride masking.

Determination of vanadium in steel, rock and ore :

The ilmenite samples were collected from Hornbendite rock of Tamil Nadu and Putkapahar of M.P. (GSI samples) and bauxite from Indian Oxygen Limited. These were finely powdered (200 mesh) and obtained directly after separation and the samples were standardized previously by spectroscopic methods. The present methods are found useful and the results of the analyses by the procedures are found to agree well with each other. The amounts of vanadium present in the samples from analyses report are given in the following Table 2. The present solvent extraction method is simple and rapid over the other existing methods.

TABLE 2—ANALYSES OF ALLOY STEEL (BAS 64b), ROCK (ILMENITE) AND ORE (BAUXITE)

Methods	BAS steel 64b, certified 1.99% V	Rock (ilmenite mineral), certified 0.1% and 0.15% V	Ore (bauxite), certified >0.08%
Binary (3.1 pH)	1.97*	0.09	0.14
Binary (1.8 M HCl)	1.965	0.08	0.138
Ternary (0.16 M HCl)	1.97	0.09	0.14

*Values are average of several determinations.

References

1. A. S. BHADURI, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1956, **151**, 109.
2. A. S. BHADURI and P. RAY, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, **154**, 103.
3. S. P. BAG and A. K. CHAKRABARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 492.
4. S. P. BAG, A. B. CHATTERJEE, A. K. CHAKRABARTI and P. R. CHAKRABORTY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19A**, 1200.
5. A. K. MAJUMDER, "N-Benzoylphenylhydroxylamine and its Analogues", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1972.
6. A. M. G. MACDONALD, *Ind. Chemist*, 1960, **36**, 512.
7. M. ISHIZAKI and S. UENO, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 538.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman's, London, 1964.
9. A. RINGBOM, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1938, **115**, 332.
10. G. H. AYRES, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, **21**, 652.
11. E. B. SANDILL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience, N. Y., 1957.